

Academic Preparation Kit

2nd Small Scale Event for University Students

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Disclaimer

This Academic Preparation Kit was compiled for the 2nd Small Scale Event (SSE) for University Students of the European Youth Parliament Portugal, which will take place digitally, from the 21st to the 23rd of May, 2021.

Topic Overviews

The Topic Overviews are written by the Committee Chairpersons and serve as background material. They aim to identify the importance of the issue at hand, as well as the principal matters within it, the interconnections amongst the main actors in those matters and the actions already taken by them while offering a short look at their possible future development.

They are written with the intention of providing stimulating, yet neutral, introductions. It must be noted that the content of the Overviews does not reflect the positions of the EYP Portugal, who strongly encourages independent thinking, and are the sole responsibility of their authors. Likewise, should the event be held under the patronage of any public entities or sponsors, no claim is made that their views are in any way represented by the contents of this preparation kit.

Links

Regarding the suggestions of research links, the list is by no means exhaustive. Also, several of the websites may contain relevant information other than the one cited herewith. Several links have been made available. Please note that the EYP Portugal is not responsible for the contents of the various websites; the texts, images and/or audio or video clips reflect the opinions of their authors, only. We recommend that you save this preparation kit on the computer or tablet that you will use during the event, together with all the research you will conduct on your own and make all those materials available for you during the event.

Wishing you a good read and successful preparation,

Teresa Sandeman

President of EYP Portugal

João Lopes

Head-Organiser of the 2nd SSE
for University Students

Leonor Rodrigues

President of the 2nd SSE
for University Students

EU Explained

I. What is the EU?

The European Union (EU) is a unique economic and political partnership between 27 European countries called 'Member States' which, together, cover much of the continent. The EU was created in the aftermath of World War II to foster economic cooperation and, thereby, peace – the idea being that countries who trade with one another become economically interdependent and, as such, more likely to avoid conflict. The result was the European Economic Community (EEC), created in 1958, between six countries: Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, Luxembourg and the Netherlands. Since then, and following various **enlargements**, a large single market has been created and continues to develop toward its full potential.

On June 23rd, 2016, the United Kingdom decided by referendum to leave the European Union, which triggered a process which is often referred to as the 'Article 50 proceedings'. After negotiating the future relationship of the UK with the EU was affected, resulting in the UK leaving the Union in 2020 and, therefore, the EU currently has a total of 27 Member States.

From Economic to Political Union

What began as a purely economic union has evolved into an organisation spanning many policy areas, from development aid to environment. A name change from EEC to EU, in 1993, reflected exactly that. The EU is based on the rule of law: everything it does is founded on treaties (see below, under 'VI. The Treaties'), voluntarily and democratically agreed by all **Member States**. These binding agreements set out the EU's goals in its many areas of activity.

Mobility, Growth, Stability, Single Currency

The EU has delivered half a century of peace, stability and prosperity, helped raise living standards and launched a single European currency, the **Euro**.

Thanks to the abolition of border controls between the EU Member States located in the Schengen zone, people can travel freely throughout most of the continent, and it has become much easier to live and work abroad in Europe.

The single or 'internal' market is the EU's main economic engine, enabling most goods, services, money and people to move freely. It remains an objective to develop this market further.

Human Rights and Equality

One of the EU's main goals is to promote human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and respect for human rights, both internally and around the world. Since the Treaty of Lisbon entered into force, in 2009, the **Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union** brings all these rights together in a single document. The EU's institutions are legally bound to uphold them, as are the governments of all Member States.

EU Explained

Transparent and Democratic Institutions

As it continues to grow, the EU remains focused on making its governing institutions more transparent and democratic. More powers are being given to the directly elected European Parliament, while national parliaments are being given a greater role, working alongside the European institutions. In turn, European citizens have an ever-increasing number of channels for taking part in the political process.

II. How does the EU work?

The institutional structure of the EU cannot be compared to that of any other international organisations (e.g., the North Atlantic Treaty Organization or the United Nations). It is neither a centralised unity like a nation state, nor does it imitate a relatively loose structure, such as the Commonwealth of Nations or a confederation like the United States of America – it is an organisation sui generis. The structure is unique and continuously developed. The Treaty of Lisbon marks the last big step in this process.

III. Main Institutions

3.1 Within the institutional triangle

EUROPEAN COMMISSION

The **European Commission** (EC) is the ‘executive’ power of the EU. One Commissioner is appointed by each Member State (with one, currently Ursula von der Leyen, being the President of the EC). The Commissioners are appointed by their respective Member States, approved by the European Parliament and put in charge of specific issues (e.g., Elisa Ferreira, the Spanish Commissioner, is responsible for Cohesion and Reforms).

The EC monitors the Member States’ and the Union’s adherence to the **acquis communautaire** (the ensemble of all EU legislation), represents the Union in its foreign relations (especially through one of its Vice-presidents, Josep Borrell Fontelles, who is also the **High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy**) and has the exclusive Right of Initiative - the right to propose laws. In the EU, the EC has the right to propose Regulations and Directives to the European Parliament and to the Council of the European Union.

The term ‘Commission’ is also used to refer to the full administrative body of over 20,000 staff members working in various **Directorates-General** (DGs) or services, each responsible for a particular policy area and headed by a Director-General, who reports directly to the President. The DGs draft laws, but their proposals become official only once the College of Commissioners adopts them during its weekly meetings.

EU Explained

EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT

The **European Parliament** (EP) is the first part of the EU's legislative branch and consists of 751 Members of Parliament (MEPs) elected for five-year mandates by all EU citizens (over 18 years old, in Austria over 16). The first direct EP election was held in 1979 and the latest took place in 2014.

The EP is divided into seven large **political groups** plus several independent MEPs. The three largest are the European People's Party (EPP), followed by the Party of European Socialists (PES) and by the Alliance of Liberals and Democrats Party (ALDE). It works either in a big **plenary** or in its 20 **Standing Committees**, each responsible for specific issue areas. The EP shares its legislative competences with the Council of the European Union.

COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION (COUNCIL OF MINISTERS)

Also known as 'the Council', the **Council of the EU** is structured in issue-specific groups (**councils**) comprising the respective Ministers of the Member States (e.g., the Council for Justice and Home Affairs). The 'president' in office supplies the different councils with a Chairperson, with the exception of the council on Foreign Affairs, which is presided to by the High Representative.

The issue areas are mirrored in those of the EP (e.g., environment, education, economy, budget), with whom the Council shares its legislative competences. Additionally, the Council also has executive powers. The Member States holding the presidency work together in groups of three, called 'trios', a system that was introduced by the Treaty of Lisbon. The trio set long-term goals and prepared a common agenda determining the topics and major issues that will be addressed by the Council over an 18-month period. On the basis of this programme, each of the three countries prepares its own more detailed six-month programme. The current trio is made up of Germany, Portugal (the current president) and Slovenia.

3.2 Outside the institutional triangle

EUROPEAN COUNCIL

The **European Council** (no standard abbreviation is used) is an EU institution comprising the heads of state or government of the Member States, along with the Council's own President (Charles Michel, since December 2019) and the President of the European Commission (Ursula von der Leyen, since November 2019). The High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy takes part in its meetings. The European Council was established as an informal body in 1975; it became an official EU institution when the Treaty of Lisbon entered into force.

While the European Council has no formal legislative power, it is charged under the Treaty of Lisbon with defining "the general political directions and priorities" of the Union. It is thus the Union's strategic (and crisis-solving) body, acting as the collective presidency of the EU.

EU Explained

EUROPEAN CENTRAL BANK

The European Central Bank (ECB) is the central bank for the Euro and administers the monetary policy of the Euro Area, which consists of 19 Member States and is one of the largest currency areas in the world. It is one of the world's most important central banks. The bank was established by the Treaty of Amsterdam, in 1998, and is headquartered in Frankfurt, Germany. Since 2019 (and until 2027), the President of the ECB has been Christine Lagarde, former managing director of International Monetary Fund. The owners and shareholders of the European Central Bank are the central banks of the 27 Member States of the EU.

COURT OF JUSTICE OF THE EUROPEAN UNION

The **Court of Justice of the European Union** (CJEU) is an EU institution that encompasses the whole judiciary. Seated in Luxembourg, it consists of two major courts and a number of specialised courts. The institution was originally established in 1952 as the Court of Justice of the European Coal and Steel Communities (as of 1958, the Court of Justice of the European Communities (CJEC)), changing to its current name with the entry into force of the Treaty of Lisbon. Its mission is to ensure that “the law is observed [...] in the interpretation and application” of the Treaties. The Court reviews the legality of the acts of any EU institution, ensures that the Member States comply with obligations under the Treaties and interprets EU law at the request of national courts. In order for a case to be brought to the CJEU, first the national legal measures applicable to the case must be exhausted, which means that no higher national appeal is possible.

It consists of two major courts: i) the **European Court of Justice** (created in 1952), the highest court in the EU legal system; ii) the General Court (created in 1988; formerly, the Court of First Instance).

3.3 Not an EU body!

COUNCIL OF EUROPE

The **Council of Europe** (CoE) is an international organisation promoting cooperation amongst all countries of Europe in the areas of legal standards, human rights, democratic development, the rule of law and cultural cooperation. It was founded in 1949, has 47 Member States with over 800 million citizens, and is an entirely separate body from the EU. The CoE does not make binding laws.

Its best-known bodies are the **European Court of Human Rights** (ECHR), which enforces the **European Convention on Human Rights**, and the **European Directorate for the Quality of Medicines**, which, through the European Pharmacopoeia Commission, sets the quality standards for pharmaceutical products in Europe. The Council of Europe's work has resulted in standards, charters and conventions

EU Explained

to facilitate cooperation between European countries.

Its statutory institutions are the Committee of Ministers (comprising the foreign ministers of each of its 47 Member States), the Parliamentary Assembly (composed of MPs from the parliaments of each Member State) and the Secretary General (Marija Pejčinović Burić).

IV. What can the EU do?

Exclusive competences – as per Article 2 (1) and Article 3 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU)

In these areas, only the EU may legislate and adopt legally binding acts. Exceptions are possible if the EU empowers Member States to act, or with regard to the implementation of Union acts.

- The customs union, including an internal free trade area with common customs tariffs (Art. 31 TFEU).
- The monetary policy of the EU for the Member States whose currency is the euro, overseen by the European Central Bank and with certain precepts formulated in the Stability and Growth Pact (Art. 129 (3) and (4), Arts. 132, 138, 219 TFEU).
- Competition rules controlling state aid from national governments and the actions of companies necessary for the functioning of the internal market.
- A common international trade policy, e.g., a common position in international trade negotiations (Art. 207 TFEU).
- The conclusion of certain international agreements (Art. 3 (2) TFEU).
- Common commercial policy.
- The conservation of marine biological resources (part of the Common Fisheries Policy, Art. 38 (1) TFEU).

Shared EU competences – as per Article 2 (2) and Article 4 TFEU.

These are policy areas on which the Member States have agreed to act individually if the EU has not exercised (or planned to exercise) its competence. If a policy area is neither exclusive nor falls under supportive actions, it is a shared competence. Some examples are: i) internal market; ii) economic, social and territorial cohesion; iii) agriculture and fishing (except the conservation of marine biological resources); iv) social policy; v) transport; vi) environment, pollution and energy; vii) consumer protection; viii) area of freedom, Security and Justice.

Supporting, coordinating or complementary competences – as per Article 2 (5) and Article 6 TFEU.

The EU can financially support the actions of the Member States that have agreed to coordinate their domestic policies through the EU. This, however, does not entail harmonisation of regulations. These areas include: i) education, vocational training, youth and sport; ii) tourism; iii) administrative cooperation; iv) civil protection; v) protection and improvement of human health; vi) industry; vii) culture.

EU Explained

V. Legal Acts of the EU

While the EU can issue several types of legal acts, not all are fully binding for Member States. These acts, named according to their legal strength, are divided into:

Regulations – have to be strictly adhered to in all Member States and leave no room for adjustments during the implementation process.

Directives – provide a framework and give a certain policy direction, leaving the Member States with more flexibility and room for adjustments.

Decisions – always address certain recipients and are only valid for those specific countries/institutions.

Recommendations – without legal force, but negotiated and voted on according to the appropriate procedure, they are not binding for the Member States.

Opinions – similar to recommendations in that they have no legal force, but not voted on, simply emitted.

The European legislative procedure runs considerably longer than those of most Member States. In brief: the EC (which has the exclusive Right to Initiative), the Council and the EP decide if the proposal becomes a legal act after having discussed relevant details. General policy guidelines and statements, especially from the EP, are formulated in Resolutions. They can entail instructions for future procedures, as well as regulations, which are formally valid in the Member States. Legal acts passed by the EP and the Council enter into force once the national governments have transposed them into national law.

VI. The Treaties

To read more, and in greater detail, about the EU, please refer to the texts of i) the **Treaty of Lisbon**; ii) the **Treaty on European Union** (TEU); iii) the **Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union** (TFEU).

Session Theme

“Ad astra per aspera” (Through adversity to the stars)

"I had initially saved this sentence after reading “To Kill a Mockingbird” by Harper Lee. This book underlines how important it is to see things from each person’s point of view and how we really never understand someone until “you climb into his skin and walk around in it”. With diversity and inclusion gaining more importance day by day in the EYP network I felt like it was not only relevant but also of extreme importance to create a theme that would encompass both these values and allow for a better understanding of them. This theme also represents a bit of what EYP has been about the past year: with Covid-19 posing as an adversity, the network never stopped working towards the creation of a new format for the sessions. And here we are, still trying.

Great hopes and great dreams have always been a driving force in EYP. I love the idea of challenging yourself and think beyond borders, beyond what is expected of you as a young adult. However, this may be hard when the world is pulling you down. I once saw in a movie that the farthest distance is between where you are and where you thought you were going to be. This isn’t inherently bad, it’s different. But in the good times, it is easier to think you can accomplish everything. It is easier to believe that the distance that separates you from where you are now and the place you want to be is not that long. So my hope for this event is that each participant believes that this distance, separating adversities from the stars, is not that long. It is reachable for every one of us. I also hope that they feel present in the change we see happening and believe they are capable of taking an active part in it. Through adversity to the stars."

The President of the 2nd SSE for University Students,
Leonor Rodrigues

Committee Topics

EMPL

The Office: In light of uneven development causing mass migration to different European Union countries for employment, what should the European Union do to tackle brain drain from certain Members States, enable the easier transition from education to the labour market for young people, and ensure an even distribution of employment opportunities across the European Union?

By Petar Rajković (RS)

ITRE

Interstellar: Considering the recent political agreement between the European Parliament and the Council, concerning the establishment of the EU's space programme for 2021-2027, what steps should be taken to benefit from space exploration, while ensuring sustainable access and use?

By Nathan Zeevenhoven (NL)

TRAN

The Tourist: Extended travel restrictions due to COVID-19 have brought the tourism sector to a global pause, resulting in unprecedented revenue losses for the tourism businesses. Taking into account that, previous to the pandemic, the growth of mass tourism had been negatively impacting Europe's top travel destinations, how can the EU support Member States in rebuilding their tourism industry, while promoting sustainability?

By Sofia Cruz (PT)

Committee Topics

CULT

Good Luck Charlie: Since 1990, children have become less able to produce unique and unconventional ideas. In a generation where innovation and entrepreneurship are the keys to future development, how should the EU foster innovation in the workforce, while also promoting creativity inside its educational systems?

By Inês Rodrigues (PT)

IMCO

Not a Game: The video game industry has overtaken film as the largest entertainment industry in the world, with 2.3 billion gamers globally. This boom is in part due to the growth of randomised in-game purchases and excessive monetisation. What can Europe do to protect both children and adults from abusive and addictive mechanics which blur the lines between gambling and gaming?

By Maria Eduarda Leite (PT)

LIBE

Not modern, just a family: Taking into consideration the varying national laws on same-sex marriage and adoption and the gap in the recognition of these families between Member-States, what course of action should the EU follow to ensure consistent family rights in its jurisdiction?

By Kostiantyn Varvaryk (UA)

EMPL

Committee on Employment and Social Affairs

The Office: In light of uneven development causing mass migration to different European Union countries for employment, what should the European Union do to tackle brain drain from certain Member States, enable the easier transition from education to the labour market for young people, and ensure an even distribution of employment opportunities across the European Union?

By Petar Rajković (RS)

Committee on Employment and Social Affairs (EMPL)

“The Office: In light of uneven development causing mass migration to different European Union countries for employment, what should the European Union do to tackle brain drain from certain Member States, enable the easier transition from education to the labour market for young people, and ensure an even distribution of employment opportunities across the European Union?”

by Petar Rajković (RS)

Relevance of the topic

A total of **3.9 million immigrants** were reported to have arrived in a Member State during 2018, while 2.6 million emigrants were reported to have left a Member State. Of those 3.9 million, 2.4 million were from non-EU member countries while 1.4 million were from another Member State. Migration is a process that generally yields positive results for the economy, and its prevalence in the EU is mostly due to the **European Single Market** which allows any European citizen to migrate to any European country on varying grounds bringing many advantages, but also disadvantages. However, this phenomenon has also increased disparities between the Member States. Lacking what some consider favourable opportunities and committed political leadership, some countries are restrained, losing their hard workers and their brightest but developing through remittances. Simultaneously, other countries grow economically by gaining more highly skilled workers but facing challenges regarding integration and social harmony.

Figure 1.4: Distribution of immigrants by citizenship, 2018
(% of all immigrants)

(1) Estimate.
(2) Provisional.

Core concepts

- **Brain drain** - the phenomenon in which large numbers of educated and very skilled people leave their own country to live and work in another one where pay and living conditions are more favourable.
- **Immigration** - is the action by which a person establishes his or her usual residence in the territory of a Member State for a period that is, or is expected to be, of at least 12 months, having previously been usually resident in another Member State or a third country. An **immigrant** is a person undertaking immigration.
- **Emigration** - is the action by which a person, having previously been usually resident in the territory of a Member State, ceases to have his or her usual residence in that Member State for a period that is, or is expected to be, of at least 12 months. An **emigrant** is a person undertaking emigration.
- **The European Single Market** - refers to the EU as one territory without any internal borders or other regulatory obstacles to the free movement of goods and services. A functioning single market stimulates competition and trade, improves efficiency, raises quality, and helps cut prices. It encompasses the EU27 as well as – with certain exceptions – Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway through the **Agreement on the European Economic Area (EEA)**, and Switzerland through bilateral treaties.
- **Free movement** - it allows EU citizens to look for a job in another EU country and work there without needing a work permit, reside there for that purpose, stay there even after employment has finished, and enjoy equal treatment with nationals in access to employment, working conditions and all other social and tax advantages. In addition to the EU27, it also applies to Iceland, Liechtenstein and Norway through the Agreement on the **EEA**, and Switzerland through bilateral treaties.
- **Donor countries** - mostly consist of EU countries with negative net migration whose nationals make up the highest number of immigrants. Those countries include Romania, Poland, Italy, Greece, Portugal, Slovakia and Bulgaria.
- **Host countries** - represent the EU countries to which citizens from donor countries migrate. Those countries include Germany, Luxembourg, Spain, France, Norway, Sweden, Austria, Belgium and the Netherlands.

Stakeholders and measures in place

The **European Single Market** and the [Freedom of movement](#) implemented by the **European Commission** are the driving force for intra-European migration putting the Member States in a key role for regulation. Host Integrated Communities Strategy policies and restructuring required to stabilise their economic situation and reduce levels of brain drain.

The welfare of migrants is tackled on different levels. The European-wide [EURES network](#) launched in 1994 provides employment support to any citizen benefiting from freedom of movement. The network has always worked hard to ensure that European citizens can benefit from the same opportunities, despite language barriers, cultural differences, bureaucratic

challenges, diverse employment laws and a lack of recognition of educational certificates across Europe.

National and international **Non-Government Organisations (NGOs)** such as the members of the [European NGO Platform on Asylum and Migration \(EPAM\)](#) lead initiatives on migrant integration and improving social conditions in donor countries. **EPAM** itself is the meeting place of all European NGOs and networks seeking to contribute to the development of asylum and migration policy in the European Union. The Platform has been running on a voluntary basis since 1994. Quarterly meetings are co-chaired by the **Churches' Commission for Migrants in Europe (CCME)** and **United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR)**, while quarterly working groups on asylum and migration are chaired respectively by the **European Council on Refugees and Exiles (ECRE)** and the **Migration Policy Group (MPG)**.

Apart from EU-wide NGOs and bodies, local authorities are also, if willing, competent to pre-empt pressures regarding social cohesion. The **Committee of the Regions** involves local authorities in the European decision-making process, conducting key discussions on migration.

Finally, **EU citizens** are perhaps the main stakeholder. The migrants' responsibility and willingness to integrate into their country of choice, along with the host countries' approach to welcoming them and supporting their integration are what defines European communities, and therefore the European Union itself.

Key conflicts

The decision of citizens to migrate is based on the [standard of living](#) and [opportunities](#) available in host countries and comparison to those in other EU countries. Some donor countries suffer from [corruption and underemployment](#) which reduces the quality in some of their critical systems such as [education and healthcare](#), creating an even bigger difference between them and host countries, which only further bolsters migration.

[Net migration rate in Europe by country in 2017](#)

Seeking a better livelihood in another Member State, migrants increase the level of **brain drain**. Countries lose specialists and highly educated young people that could have generated direct national economic prosperity, instead of [through remittances](#). Demographic disadvantages are also at play. With increased emigration and low birth rates, donor countries decrease in population and rely on older workers. This makes state pensions less sustainable as there are fewer working-age citizens to pay for the pensions of older, retired citizens.

[Disparities in minimum wages across the EU](#)

Migrant workers make important contributions to the labour market in both high and low skilled occupations. However, many migrate without properly considering the challenges they may face in a different Member State. A paradox is created, where finding work proves to be difficult due to the [recognition of foreign qualifications](#) and language barriers. Since there is no automatic recognition of academic diplomas on an EU-wide scale, highly educated job seekers are forced to find a job they are overqualified for or change their career path entirely.

In host countries, migrants [contribute more in taxes and social contributions than they receive](#) in individual benefits. Nonetheless, even with a secured job, obtaining healthcare and social welfare benefits is [complicated](#) across the EU. The ongoing refugee crisis places the priority on providing support to vulnerable groups. Finally, discrimination against movers hinders their integration. Social abuse and exclusion of groups, such as the Roma, lead to ghettoisation and fuels civil

discord. On this basis, far-right political parties promote xenophobia, anti-migration policies and support Euroscepticism, convincing citizens into losing faith in the EU, as seen with BREXIT.

Donor countries have also taken action to incentivise citizens to stay in their country of origin, such as Governmental initiatives in Baltic countries like [Work in Estonia](#) or [Study in Estonia](#). However, challenges with implementation have led to [backfire cases](#). The Committee of the Regions suggests countries [invest in education](#) with support from European funds, hence internationalising education and allowing faster recognition and equivalence of qualifications. Additionally, Member States can also tackle the issue of corruption and provide satisfactory social welfare systems.

Food for thought

Why do people migrate? Who benefits from migration? Which problems do immigrants face when they arrive in their host countries? What about when they look for a job? Can these problems be prevented? If the answer is “yes”, how? Who should be the one assisting migrants? Should it be the EU, the donor country, or the host country? Try to explain in one sentence how the process of brain drain can be stopped.

- [Exploring migration causes – why people migrate - European Parliament \(2020\)](#)
- [How migration can make the world richer - The Economist \(2019\)](#)
- [Is the EU's Single Market leading to convergence or divergence? - Center for European Reform, Simon Tilford \(2017\)](#)
- [Intra-EU Migration: The Challenge of Social Cohesion - EUCAnetwith Dr Michael John \(2015\)](#)
- [Is migration good for the economy? - OECD \(2014\)](#)

Introductory Clauses

- A. Aware that 1.4 million people have migrated between Member States in 2018,
- B. Alarmed by the disparity between minimum wages across the EU,
- C. Noting with regret the high levels of corruption in certain Member States,
- D. Deeply concerned by the negative and inconsistent net migration rate in certain Member States,
- E. Disturbed by the lack of widely automatic recognition of academic diplomas and certificates across Member States,
- F. Bearing in mind the expanding difference in the quality of education and healthcare between Member States,
- G. Aware that the demographic disadvantages faced by donor countries lead to an over-reliance on older workers and reduce the sustainability of state pension systems,

ITRE

Committee on Industry, Research and Energy

Interstellar: Considering the recent political agreement between the European Parliament and the Council, concerning the establishment of the EU's space programme for 2021-2027, what steps should be taken to benefit from space exploration, while ensuring sustainable access and use?

By Nathan Zeevenhooven (NL)

Committee on Industry, Research and Energy - ITRE

*“**Interstellar:** Considering the recent political agreement between the European Parliament and the Council, concerning the establishment of the EU's space programme for 2021-2027, what steps should be taken to benefit from space exploration, while ensuring sustainable access and use?”*

by Nathan Zeevenhooven (NL)

Relevance of the topic

In December 2020, the European Council and European Parliament finalised the regulation for the [EU space programme for 2021-2027](#). With this programme, the EU hopes to advance its position in space exploration and strengthen its **autonomy** among other key players, such as the United States, Russia and China. Until now, the [European Space Agency \(ESA\)](#) had to rely on the United States and Russia for transport to and from space, as well as communications and other infrastructure, which is why it aims to become more independent. This piece of legislation comes at a time when many **private and public organisations** are fighting for a place on the launchpad. For example, NASA is actively planning to [send astronauts back to the Moon before 2028](#), as well as expand its Mars flight schedule. A central motivating factor for the EU to advance its space program is **scientific research and innovation**, however this ambition doesn't come without the necessary hurdles: the burning of rocket fuel during launches is **environmentally harmful**, rocket launches are incredibly **expensive**, and **space debris** is piling up outside of the atmosphere. Therefore, it is essential that the EU's strategy on space takes **sustainability** and responsible space travel into account, while keeping the goals of the framework intact.

Core concepts

- **[Space exploration](#)**: The act of sending crewed and uncrewed spacecraft beyond Earth's atmosphere to gain and expand human knowledge about outer space.
- **[Sustainability](#)**: The ability to meet our current needs, without compromising the chances and abilities of future generations to meet their needs. This concerns natural, social and economic resources.
- **[Space debris](#)**: Human made objects that are discarded in space, consisting of decommissioned satellites, discarded rocket launch stages and fragments of items that burnt up in the atmosphere. Most of these objects are in a constant orbit around Earth, posing a collision hazard to spacecraft, satellites and space stations.
- **[Orbit](#)**: A path of an object around a star, planet or moon. An orbit happens because the object, which is travelling at speed, is constantly being attracted by the gravitational force of the central body.

Stakeholders and measures in place

The [European Council](#) and the [European Parliament](#) put forth the [EU space programme for 2021-2027](#) to expand the EU's presence in space travel and exploration, making the EU a more central player in space, as well as more autonomous from other countries for their space infrastructure. Lastly, the proposing actors hope to centralise all activities of the EU in space, which creates a more accessible platform for investors.

The [European Space Agency \(ESA\)](#) is an organisation that consists of [22 EU Member States](#) and is responsible for space exploration, carrying out missions in the interest of the EU and its **Member States** to perform research and explore space

Private companies such as [SpaceX](#) and [Blue Origin](#) are competing heavily over mission contracts from space agencies, working alongside [NASA](#) to develop spacecraft for the next moon landings, as well as other missions. The **ESA** also works closely with Member States to help them achieve their goals and coordinate with other central stakeholders.

Copernicus, Galileo & EGNOS are three large projects from the **ESA**, currently ongoing in space. [Copernicus](#) is a programme that enables scientists to accurately observe Earth, especially focusing on climate change and natural disasters; [Galileo](#) is a satellite navigation system, allowing Member States to use their own GPS system, instead of alternatives from the **United States** or **Russia**; lastly, [EGNOS](#) is a satellite navigation network suitable for high precision use, such as maneuvering planes and ships.

In 2007, the [EU](#) made its first policy suggestion on space exploration, the [Resolution on the European Space Policy](#). This was the first time the EU, as a collective, had designed a space policy framework, instead of each Member State doing so for themselves. The aim of this framework was to better coordinate EU Member States' activities in space and to efficiently organise their respective roles in EU space exploration.

The [five United Nations treaties on outer space](#) are the largest international agreements on the use of, and behavior in, outer space. The "[Outer Space Treaty](#)" concerns the governance of activities of states in the exploration and use of outer space, being the most important one.

Key conflicts

Considering that space exploration has a very large impact on the **environment, sustainability** is a key point in this topic. as. More specifically, SpaceX's Falcon Heavy rocket, for example, uses 440 tonnes of kerosine-derived fuel, emitting **CO2 gases** during combustion, which, the current launch frequency into account, is still a relatively small amount.

However, SpaceX is planning on **launching a rocket every two weeks** in the future, meaning that if these rockets were to use the same fuel, they would pose an enormous risk for the environment. This raises serious questions about whether the advantages reached by sending a rocket to space **equal out the impact** the launch has on the environment, and whether or not the impact of rocket launches can be reduced.

An alternative for kerosine-derived fuel is **liquid hydrogen** since it simply emits water vapour during combustion. However, liquid hydrogen is highly costly, its production is currently unfriendly to the environment and hard to store and contain, as the substance needs extremely low temperatures in order to keep its liquid state.

The profits of space exploration include **scientific discoveries** about our planet and other celestial bodies, **development of technologies**, such as satellites for navigation and communication, and **innovation** in other fields, such as transportation, health and public safety.

Moreover, **Space debris** also poses a large problem, as there are now more than 28160 actively tracked large items in Earth orbit, and 900000 objects ranging between 1cm and 10cm in size. Many more are smaller than that, but all of them pose a **potential collision risk** to spacecraft and satellites around the Earth. This amount is projected to increase in the future, with potentially disastrous consequences, including deadly collisions and environmental pollution. Even though there have been a few **cleanup initiatives**, they have yet to be implemented thus far.

[Amount of regularly tracked debris objects in space per orbit type](#)

Food for thought

With the environmental impact of rocket launches being a heavy burden on space organisations, should these effects be weighed more heavily in comparison to the advantages of space exploration? Are there ways in which space travel can be made progressively sustainable?

As the amount of space debris increases quickly, how can the EU best protect its spacecraft from such debris? Should cleanup be prioritised over further exploration of space?

- [**Sustainability in Space Travel: How Does Space Exploration Impact the Environment?**](#) - Thomasnet
- [**Liquid Hydrogen--the Fuel of Choice for Space Exploration**](#) - Nasa
- [**Space debris by the numbers**](#) - ESA
- [**What is space debris and why is it a problem?**](#) - The Natural History Museum
- [**ESA commissions world's first space debris removal**](#) - ESA
- [**From space back to Earth: supporting sustainable development with spaceflight technologies**](#) - Sustainable Earth

Introductory Clauses

- A. Recognising the EU's desire to autotomize and expand its presence in space,
- B. Alarmed by the impact that the emissions from fuels' combustion of spacecraft launches have on the environment,
- C. Aware that space organisations aim to increase their launch schedule,
- D. Deeply concerned by the increasing amount of space debris orbiting the Earth its collision risks with spacecrafts,
- E. Acknowledging the various cleanup initiatives proposed by space organisations to decrease the amount of space debris in Earth's orbit,
- F. Keeping in mind the positive effects of space exploration and its impact on society,
- G. Concerned by the high production costs and difficult containment procedures of sustainable alternatives to kerosine-derived rocket fuels;

TRAN

Committee on Transport and Tourism

The Tourist: Extended travel restrictions due to COVID-19 have brought the tourism sector to a global pause, resulting in unprecedented revenue losses for the tourism businesses. Taking into account that, previous to the pandemic, the growth of mass tourism had been negatively impacting Europe's top travel destinations, how can the EU support Member States in rebuilding their tourism industry, while promoting sustainability?

By Sofia Cruz (PT)

Committee on Transport and Tourism - TRAN

*“**The Tourist:** Extended travel restrictions due to COVID-19 have brought the tourism sector to a global pause, resulting in unprecedented revenue losses for the tourism businesses. Taking into account that, previous to the pandemic, the growth of mass tourism had been negatively impacting Europe’s top travel destinations, how can the EU support Member States in rebuilding their tourism industry, while promoting sustainability?”*

by Sofia Cruz (PT)

Relevance of the topic

Before the COVID-19 pandemic, tourism was a fast-growing industry, with [26 million](#) EU citizens being employed by this sector. Yet, with tourism now being one of the sectors that have been hit the hardest by the pandemic, and the industry having no certain foreseeable future, this can be an opportunity to **rethink the tourism of the future**. Now more than ever, we are seeing the impact that the tourism sector has on the EU, and the rest of the world, and with the [80% fall of international tourism in 2020](#), it is time to start thinking about rebuilding this sector. The decrease in tourism is also [affecting EU Member States differently](#), with **countries in southern Europe**, like Greece, Portugal, Spain and Italy, **being amongst the most affected**, due to the fact that their GDP depends mainly on this sector. With the tourism industry expected to [remain in survival mode](#) well into 2021, solutions for the short to medium term are as important as solutions for the long term. So, a burning question arises: How can governments **boost and support the tourism sector** in its hour of need, while also promoting **long-lasting measures**, that will lead to stronger, safer, and more sustainable international tourism?

Core concepts

- **[Sustainability](#)**: The concept of meeting our own needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.
- **[Eco-tourism](#)**: Tourism directed towards exotic, often threatened, natural environments, intended to support conservation efforts and observe wildlife.
- **[Wellness tourism](#)**: Tourism for the purpose of promoting health and well-being through physical, psychological, or spiritual activities. Wellness tourists are proactive in seeking to improve or maintain health and quality of life, often focusing on prevention.
- **[Short-haul travel](#)**: Travelling a short distance, usually defined by a flight lasting anywhere from 30 minutes to 3 hours.

- **[Long-haul travel](#)**: Travelling a long distance, usually defined by a flight lasting beyond 6 hours.
- **[GDP](#)**: Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is the total monetary or market value of all the finished goods and services produced within a country's borders in a specific time period. As a broad measure of overall domestic production, it functions as a comprehensive scorecard of a given country's economic health.

Stakeholders and measures in place

The **[European Commission](#)** launched the **[Re-open EU](#)** platform on the 15th of June 2020, which provides a **frequently updated rundown of the coronavirus health situation in Europe**, based on data from the **[European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control \(ECDC\)](#)**. This platform was one of the measures announced by the Commission in its **[Tourism and Transport package](#)**, in order to help the development of the tourism sector and allow safe travels to continue in the EU while following the necessary health precautions. On March 17th, 2021, the Commission also adopted a legislative proposal that established a common structure for a **[Digital Green Certificate](#)** that covers vaccination, testing and recovery. This is an **[EU level approach](#)** to issuing, verifying, and accepting certificates, to facilitate free movement within the EU, based on strict respect for non-discrimination and the fundamental rights of EU citizens. In mid-June of 2021, a technical framework defined at EU level is to be put in place, in order to ensure security, interoperability, as well as full compliance with personal data protection.

Some **Member States** have promoted **[contact tracing and warning apps](#)** that can be voluntarily installed with the purpose of **warning the users in case of having been in the proximity of a person who has been tested positive for coronavirus**. These apps may also provide relevant information from health authorities, such as advice to get tested or to self-isolate, and who to contact.

On October 13th, 2020, Member States adopted a **[Council Recommendation](#)** on a coordinated approach to the restriction of free movement in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. This proposal sets out **four key areas** where Member States should work closer together: common criteria and thresholds for Member States when deciding whether to introduce travel restrictions; mapping of common criteria using an agreed colour code; a common framework for measures applied to travellers from high-risk areas, and clear and timely information to the public about any restrictions.

The **[Council of the European Union](#)** updated its **[recommendation](#)** on travel restrictions from third countries into the EU, on February 2nd, 2021. EU countries should require people travelling for any essential or non-essential reason to have a **negative [PCR test taken at the earliest 72 hours before departure](#)**, except for transport and frontier workers.

The [European Consumer Centre Network](#) provides [advice and assistance](#) to citizens on consumers' rights on cross-border issues. This includes hotel or travel bookings affected by the coronavirus pandemic, as well as consumer-related situations that may arise abroad.

On August 25th, 2021, [WHO](#) presented a [document](#) about COVID-19 management in hotels and other entities of the accommodation sector. In this document, you will find different measures the WHO advises regarding cleaning and housekeeping; reception and concierge; restaurants, breakfast and dining rooms and bars; etc.

The [International Council of Museums](#) (ICOM) released a [document](#) providing suggestions for actions that museums and museum professionals can take to support community resilience during and after the COVID-19 crisis as well as examples of museum initiatives and useful resources within the current context of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Key conflicts

Although the tourism sector is struggling at the moment and will [continue to struggle for the rest of the year](#), lifting measures too quickly could cause a **rise in infections** and hospitalisation of people. Whilst the vaccination process is ongoing, the need for travel, tourism and the benefits that come with them (generation of wealth, development of countries, job creation etc.) must still be **weighed against the risks of facilitating the spread of the virus** and a resurgence of cases, which could require reintroduction of confinement measures.

[Europe's visitor arrivals declines](#)

For many Member States, tourism is a key contributor to the economic and social sectors as it provides much-needed jobs and income, often concentrated in regions with **no alternative sources of employment** and involving **low-skilled workers**. Unfortunately, this ecosystem has been hit hard by the halt in tourism activities, and with the tourism sector previously providing [26 million jobs within the EU](#), action needs to be taken in order to support the people that rely on this industry to make a living.

Taking into account that travel as we know it probably **will not be the same as it once was**, it's time to start imagining the travel of the short-term and long-term future and what this could mean in terms of the environment and sustainability. The travel restrictions imposed by governments have forced people to think outside the box when it comes to travelling during the COVID-19 pandemic, with [people choosing short-haul travel, usually within their own country](#). Cities have become quieter, UNESCO World Heritage Sites haven't been over-crowded, and the skies have been less polluted. The planet has had a chance to breathe, and although the tourism industry has been suffering massively, **going back to the way things were also proves to be unsustainable** in the long haul.

Lastly, the **ongoing COVID-19 pandemic** has revealed gaps in government and industry preparedness and response capacity, and while **flexible policy solutions are needed** to enable the tourism industry to exist alongside the virus in the short to medium term, it is also crucial to look beyond this and **take concrete steps to learn and improve from the crisis**.

Food for thought

How can the EU benefit from this pandemic, turning the tourism crisis into a more sustainable industry in the long-term, while also supporting it in the short to medium term?

How can the EU benefit from the digitalisation of travel during the coronavirus pandemic, while continuing to support local workers?

Should there be closer cooperation between Member States in tackling international travel issues?

Will longer, well thought out itineraries in open spaces become the travel of the future? Or will people go back to choosing resorts in countries they've been to several times before?

For further research:

- [Rebuilding tourism for the future: COVID-19 policy responses and recovery](#), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
- [What will travel look like in a post-Covid world?](#), Jenny Southan
- [Latest COVID-19 travel restrictions in Europe](#), EuroNews.travel
- [Travel during the coronavirus pandemic](#), European Commission
- [Re-open EU](#), European Union
- [Communication from the Commission regarding Tourism and Transport - 2020 and beyond](#), European Commission
- [How Europe is tackling mass tourism](#), DW

- [Infographic - A common approach on COVID-19 travel measures](#), Council of the European Union
- [COVID-19: EU Guidance for the progressive resumption of tourism services and for health protocols in hospitality establishments](#), European Commission

Introductory Clauses

- A. Aware that the tourism industry accounts for [26 million jobs in the EU](#),
- B. Deeply concerned by the fact that [travelling facilitates the spread](#) of the Covid-19 virus,
- C. Noting with concern that [communities whose GDP mostly depend on revenue](#) from the tourism sector,
- D. Reaffirming the potential of the [digitalisation of travel](#),
- E. Alarmed by the [unsustainability of the tourism sector](#) regarding:
 - i. the damage to the natural environment,
 - ii. the high levels of carbon emissions that result from the frequent and increased use of cars, trains, and airplanes,
 - iii. the commodification of culture,
 - iv. the decline of living standards of local residents,
- F. Emphasising the need to adapt tourists' [travel tendencies from before the Covid-19 pandemic](#), with more conscious and deliberate choices,
- G. Contemplating the [newest travel trends](#), such as:
 - i. short-haul travel within citizens' own countries,
 - ii. longer vacation periods, where citizens can combine leisure and work,
 - iii. trips that allow respectful and safe engagement with the local communities;

CULT

Committee on Culture and Education

Good Luck Charlie: Since 1990, children have become less able to produce unique and unconventional ideas. In a generation where innovation and entrepreneurship are the keys to future development, how should the EU foster innovation in the workforce, while also promoting creativity inside its educational systems?

By Inês Rodrigues (PT)

Committee on Culture and Education - CULT

*“**Good Luck Charlie:** Since 1990, children have become less able to produce unique and unconventional ideas. In a generation where innovation and entrepreneurship are the keys to future development, how should the EU foster innovation in the workforce, while also promoting creativity inside its educational systems?”*

by Inês Rodrigues (PT)

Relevance of the topic

In 2011, researcher Kyung Hee Kim published an article on what she called [“The creativity crisis”](#), elaborating on how children and young adults are facing a **decrease in creative and original thinking**. However, different [studies](#) also point out that kids are becoming more imaginative since the 1980s. In a world constantly and rapidly changing, the lack of creativity among youngsters becomes a demanding challenge that societies must address. This paradigm then poses a particular question: can creativity disappear? Experts refuse that theory, claiming that **creativity can only be [suppressed in distinct contexts](#)**. As an example, in schools, the standardisation of testing and the pressure of completing national curricula does **not leave much room for innovative thoughts and initiatives. Innovation and creativity play an essential role in the [development of children](#)**, as they create self-confidence and provide a wide range of problem-solving and motor skills that are needed in tomorrow’s world. Bearing in mind that **[innovation is not something that can be successfully mandated](#)**, it falls upon the Member States the responsibility of creating opportunities and incentives for schools to design different and better learning experiences. Moreover, **[the COVID-19 pandemic has made schools and governments rethink education](#)**, as schools needed to adapt to digital settings. Could this be, after all, a turning point for educational systems as we know them?

Core concepts

- [Educational System](#) comprises everything that goes into education, from schools, funding, administration, human resources, learning material, laws and regulations, among others.
- [Entrepreneurship](#) refers to the act of creating a business or company, seeking to make a profit and/or a difference in the world.
- [Innovation](#) is the process of implementing or improving a product, good, service, or method. In practical terms, it can be a new marketing method or a new organisational method in business practices, workplace organisation or external relations.
- The [Education Workforce](#) are the people responsible for teaching, but also for making school improvements possible.

Stakeholders and measures in place

The **European Commission's [Directorate-General for Education and Culture](#)** is responsible for supporting the **education sector and its policies**, encouraging various projects and programmes, notably Creative Europe and Erasmus+. The European Commission has also established a **[European Education Area](#)**, aiming to foster the cooperation between the European Union and Member States while promoting inclusiveness and a higher quality of national education. Moreover, the **[Digital Education Action Plan \(2021-2027\)](#)** proposes a series of frameworks and guidelines to help foster the development of a high-performing digital education ecosystem, as well as enhance digital skills and competencies for digital transformation.

The **[Education Commission](#)** is a global initiative that promotes **quality education** by raising awareness and engaging with world leaders, policymakers and researchers. Its 2016 report on **[The Learning Generation: Investing in education for a changing world](#)** developed an **action plan** with **recommendations** regarding education workforce, financing, education delivery mechanisms, and transforming learning.

The **[European Institute of Innovation and Technology \(EIT\)](#)** is a European Union independent body, aimed to **strengthen the ability to innovate**. As part of the **[Horizon 2020 programme](#)**, it works closely with **[Innovation Communities](#)** to **power innovators and entrepreneurs** across Europe. Regarding education, the EIT's Innovation Communities have developed **[education portfolios](#)** that focus on delivering entrepreneurship and innovation skills.

The **[STEM Alliance](#)** brings together Ministries of Education and education stakeholders to **promote Science, Technology, Engineering and Math (STEM)** education and careers, contributing to building a skilled workforce.

Member States have a primordial role in **implementing and structuring their education policies**, with education being a **[Member States competency only](#)**. The European Union supports Member States through policy cooperation and funding instruments. Even though they have **sovereignty over their education policies**, they work in close **cooperation with the EU** to implement some of the ideas and initiatives, reflected on programmes such as Erasmus+.

The **Education Sector**, composed of public and private schools and pre-schools across Europe, also plays an important role, even though their **[autonomy](#)** can be greatly restricted by national curricula. They are responsible for **[adapting schools to local needs](#)** and specific contexts, which do elevate students and promote their creativity and innovation.

Employers appear as the ones looking for a workforce more capable of creative thinking. As over the coming decade, a **[share of newly created jobs will emerge](#)**, or existing occupations will undergo significant transformations in terms of their content and skills requirements, employers are looking for an adaptable workforce ready to solve the challenges of tomorrow.

Key conflicts

As Europe strives to **reinforce education systems** to achieve a better-prepared youth, [understanding the needs of tomorrow](#) becomes a priority. With creative and human skills acquiring greater relevance in today's society, the need for **retraining the educational workforce** is urgent. The challenge lies in adapting to the [shifting market demand skills](#). Furthermore, it is of utmost importance that the changes made in the education sector to promote innovation and creativity can also be applied to the workforce, as they are [one of its greatest levers for change](#).

Top 10 skills of 2025

[The top 10 job skills of tomorrow](#)

[Standardised testing](#) has become a valuable way of measuring and monitoring the quality of education across different countries. Programmes such as [PISA, the OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment](#), aim to help States structure their educational systems. These tests are useful to [understand and assess students' struggles](#). Moreover, they give students, parents, teachers and governments an overview of their progress and performance. Nevertheless, their overuse poses a [threat to creativity and imagination](#), as teachers discard creative projects and opportunities to complete curricula. Additionally, more standardised [testing increases stress levels among teens](#) as they face the enormous pressure of setting themselves apart from their peers.

The controversy over **education curricula** is one of the most prominent ones. Having a uniform national curriculum provides a [clear set of standards and expectations](#) about what children should learn. Likewise, it makes progress and attainment measurable and comparable on a national scale. But even though the EU offers various opportunities for creative extracurricular projects, the [rigid and restrictive national curricula](#) does not allow a personified education.

Consequently, there is a restraint of fast-moving thinking, with experts believing **schools should have the autonomy of being more reactive than prescriptive**, meaning that they should be able to adapt the curriculum to each individual's needs.

The [digitalisation of education](#) can serve as a basis for its modernisation and reform. The European Commission's set of [Digital Education Policies](#) highlights the **technological value that can be added to learning and teaching** processes. However, as Dr Kyung Hee Kim highlights, one of the reasons for a decrease in creativity is [impersonal digital communication](#). To foster creativity and innovation, a hands-on and [project-based learning](#) approach is needed.

[Desired components of Digital Learning](#)

Food for thought

How can the EU benefit from this pandemic, making it a turning point for education methodologies?

Should there be closer cooperation between Member States in uniformising educational systems?

How can schools balance national curricula with the incorporation of the different types of intelligence?

Should standardised testing be discarded? And if so, how could the academic standards be maintained?

How can the EU benefit from the digitalisation of education, while making sure no one is prejudiced due to lack of resources?

For further reading:

- [Do schools kill creativity?](#) - a TED Talk by Sir Ken Robinson
- [The Creativity Crisis: it's getting worse](#) - article by Dr. KH Kim
- [Coronavirus: The good that can come out of an upside-down world](#) - article by bbc news
- [The Education Crisis: Being in School Is Not the Same as Learning](#) - article by The World Bank

CULT

- [10 Ways Educators Can Make Classrooms More Innovative](#) - article by Forbes
- [What is the EU doing to promote innovation in education?](#) - article by the European Commission

Introductory Clauses

- A. Conscious that [creativity is as important in today's world education as literacy](#);
- B. Gravely concerned that since the 1990s there has been a [decrease in creative and original thinking](#) among children,
- C. Acknowledging that [95% of respondents](#) of the *Digital Education Action Plan* consultation consider the COVID-19 crisis to be a turning point for digital technologies in education,
- D. Noting that [rigid and restrictive national curricula](#) fails to stimulate creativity and curiosity in students,
- E. Fully aware that [standardised testing increases stress levels](#) and burnout in children,
- F. Reaffirming the value of the education workforce as one of the most important [levers for change](#),
- G. Emphasising the need to [adapt school systems to the market demand skills](#) in a world of constant and rapid change,
- H. Considering that [the current school systems fail to prioritise creativity](#);

IMCO

Committee on Internal Market and Consumer Protection

Not a Game: The video game industry has overtaken film as the largest entertainment industry in the world, with 2.3 billion gamers globally. This boom is in part due to the growth of randomised in-game purchases and excessive monetisation. What can Europe do to protect both children and adults from abusive and addictive mechanics which blur the lines between gambling and gaming?

By Maria Eduarda Leite (PT)

Committee on Internal Market and Consumer Protection (IMCO)

*“**Not a Game:** The video game industry has overtaken film as the largest entertainment industry in the world, with 2.3 billion gamers globally. This boom is in part due to the growth of randomised in-game purchases and excessive monetisation. What can Europe do to protect both children and adults from abusive and addictive mechanics which blur the lines between gambling and gaming?”*

by Maria Eduarda Leite (PT)

Relevance of the topic

According to the [World Health Organization](#) (WHO), gaming and gambling have been recognised as addictive behaviours. **Gambling Disorder** has long been included in formal classification systems but **Gaming Disorder** was only introduced as a new condition in 2019. The WHO acknowledges that there has been an increase in the co-occurrence of these two disorders. This convergence might be aided by the implementation of monetisation systems in games as a consequence of [an increase of 200% to 300% of production costs](#) for video games. These unregulated game economies have [upset the gaming community](#).

Loot boxes and other **microtransactions** are at the root of this controversy. Typically, players purchase loot boxes to obtain new characters, skins, and cosmetic items that do not affect gameplay. On the contrary, microtransactions involve buying items or characters that do affect gameplay, sometimes even providing competitive advantage - hence the pay-to-win term- over the strategy and mastery required from players. The use of loot boxes in games has been an unregulated form of online gambling and [promotes addictive behaviour](#), raising alarm over children’s early exposure to gambling.

Core concepts

- **Loot boxes:** Loot boxes can be defined as “items in video games that may be bought for real-world money, but which provide players with a randomised reward of uncertain value”.
- **Microtransaction:** Microtransaction can be defined as “a business model where users can purchase virtual items for small amounts of money”.
- **AAA games:** An informal classification that commonly indicates that a game is being produced by a large, established publisher and that it likely has a relatively large development and marketing budget. These games are usually targeted to the widest possible audience, and often include various monetisation schemes, such as microtransactions or loot boxes.

Stakeholders and measures in place

As the coordinator of international health within the United Nations (UN), the **WHO** has recognised Gambling Disorder as a mental illness, providing it with official status. The organisation classification of gaming and gambling as addictive behaviours has built the foundation to define the appropriate legal framework to tackle these problems.

Regarding the loot boxes practice, the [study requested by the IMCO committee](#) presents the policies adopted by the European Union (EU), as well as the relevant regulatory framework in the Member States and actions taken by national gambling authorities.

The European Union has both [supporting](#) and [shared](#) competencies regarding human health, along with the Member States, on consumer protection. According to the aforementioned study, the **European Commission** has not tackled the most recent gambling controversy but has been adopting several [communications and recommendations](#) about the protection of minors in the gaming and gambling context more broadly.

At a **national level**, only [Belgium and the Netherlands](#) have addressed loot boxes directly and have stated that they violate their national gambling laws, banning them from video games. Slovakia, as of May 2020, has been investigating the issue of loot boxes. In Denmark, France, Finland, and Sweden gambling regulations do not apply to loot boxes, which are regulated by the [general legislation on contracts and consumer protection](#).

Since the legal definitions of gambling vary between Member States, loot boxes are not considered gambling in the legal sense in most jurisdictions. Furthermore, the limited legal capacity of minors makes loot boxes purchases a grey area, regarding the validity of such purchases.

The **Interactive Software Federation of Europe** (ISFE) has created the [Pan European Game Information \(PEGI\)](#) label to help gamers or their parents evaluate the content and age-appropriateness of games, classifying them by different age categories and content descriptors. It aims to ensure that young people are not exposed to content unsuitable for their age. It is considered a model of European harmonisation in the field of minor protection and consumer transparency.

The **gaming industry** groups [have been rejecting claims](#) that loot boxes are gambling, [arguing that](#) the “player always gets something in return, as opposed to a slot machine”, and having been “restricting the transferability of any items granted via loot boxes”.

[European Games Developer Federation \(EGDF\)](#) welcomes all measures to be more transparent in communicating the changes in business models within games and improve tools & safeguards in place for players, parents and caregivers in digital distribution platforms.

[Example](#) proposed by EGDF on implementing data protection consent requests for minors:

HOW IT WORKS AT THE MOMENT?

HOW IT COULD WORK?

Key conflicts

According to the [study requested by the IMCO committee](#), there is a **lack of research** into loot box spending causing problematic gambling behaviour. Also, most of the research has been done on the adult population, and most studies on underaged players rely on reports from parents or self-answered by young people. The reliability and validity of these studies may be put into question since parents may not have a full grasp on their children’s behaviour, and also, some scholars consider self-answered surveys unreliable. However, there is enough evidence to conclude that loot box mechanisms and in-game purchases, in general, could be problematic for young players. Due to an insufficient ability to understand costs and probabilities and a lower control over their impulses, **children and adolescents are potentially more vulnerable** to problematic game designs, including loot boxes.

Some **problematic designs** relate to opaque pricing and offer techniques, rewards and presentational features, some of which could be addictive. This IMCO study states that these “might mislead players regarding the likelihood of receiving valuable items, and could promote addiction”.

Loot box openings and trades have also been identified as problematic. Streaming the loot boxes openings, and therefore revealing its contents to other players, can now be traded illegally with

real-world money on online marketplaces. Also, some sites have been shown to offer players loot boxes at a lower price than the originals. This opens the possibility of unregulated gambling-like activities.

It is essential to look at the big picture and recognise that the main problem lies in monetised loot boxes and other microtransactions. The **lack of regulation** for these gambling systems, and easy accessibility for children (no age restrictions, no purchase limits, no pop-up warning on excessive behaviour), makes players more vulnerable to gaming and gambling disorders at an early age.

On the other hand, there is a need to consider the companies' efforts to cover their expenses for game development. The EU could have an active role in creating the guidelines for **sustainable monetisation** on their games, targeted to the appropriate age groups.

Food for thought

- How can reward systems be more appropriate for children?
- What can the EU do to ensure that companies create monetising systems that don't pose a threat to public health?
- How should companies approach monetisation within their games?
- How can game developers fix problematic design features while maintaining an exciting gaming experience?
- Should the population be better informed on gaming and gambling disorders to prevent addictive behaviours?

Further reading:

- [How a Dutch clinic helps UK teenagers addicted to gaming](#) - The Guardian
- [Harmful internet use | Part I: Internet addiction and problematic use \(Section 5\)](#) - European Parliamentary Research Service
- [Online Gambling in the EU](#) - European Commission

Introductory Clauses

- A. Concerned with the [lack of regulation](#) around addictive practices in video games,
- B. Emphasising the existence of unregulated gambling-like activities related to loot box openings, trading and skin betting,
- C. Pointing out the insufficient research and lack of data about the relation between gaming and gambling,
- D. Noting with concern that games containing microtransactions targeted at adults are also easily available for, and played by, children,
- E. Alarmed that [60%](#) of the top mobile games on Google Play and Apple's App Store contain loot boxes, [over 90%](#) of them are rated as suitable for children aged 12+,
- F. Taking into account the gaming industry's [unwillingness to acknowledge](#) the existence of problematic design features that promote addiction;

LIBE

Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs

Not modern, just a family: Taking into consideration the varying national laws on same-sex marriage and adoption and the gap in the recognition of these families between Member-States, what course of action should the EU follow to ensure consistent family rights in its jurisdiction?

By Kostia Varvaryk (UA)

Committee on Civil Liberties, Justice and Home Affairs - LIBE

“Not modern, just a family: Taking into consideration the varying national laws on same-sex marriage and adoption and the gap in the recognition of these families between Member-States, what course of action should the EU follow to ensure consistent family rights in its jurisdiction?”

by Kostia Varvaryk (UA)

Relevance of the topic

According to the [Eurobarometer on Discrimination 2019](#), **53% of EU citizens** believe that discrimination of LGBTQI+ people – in different spheres – is a living reality in their country, still posing a big concern for Europeans.

Discrimination against the LGBTQI+ community is very noticeable in regard to marriage and adoption rights. **Only thirteen of 27 Member States recognise same-sex marriages**, while **six provide no instruments** of legal recognition for same-sex couples. Other countries recognise them partially – as **civil unions** – but **with limited rights**. That means that if, for example, a same-sex couple from France goes to Poland, and one of the partners needs to be hospitalised the other does not have a right to visit them or make health directives, as the closest family member.

Legend:

Dark-green – marriage equality

Light-green – civil unions (with rights similar to marriage)

Yellow – civil unions (with the limitation of rights)

Grey – no legal recognition

The map was created based on the data of [Rainbow Europe](#), the project of ILGA-Europe – the European Region of the International Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans and Intersex Association. Data are valid as of 2021.

Regarding adoption rights, [full joint adoption is only legal in the same 13 Member States](#) who recognise same-sex marriages. In some countries, such as Estonia and Slovenia, only step-child adoption is allowed, whilst **other EU Member States do not recognise adoption by same-sex couples**. That means that a child adopted by same-sex parents from France might not be legally recognised as theirs when the family moves to Hungary, which prohibits such a kind of adoption.

Legend:

Dark-green – full joint adoption

Light-green – step-child adoption only

Grey – no legal recognition

The map was created based on the data of [Rainbow Europe](#), the project of ILGA-Europe – the European Region of the International Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Trans and Intersex Association. Data are valid as of 2021.

Core concepts

- **Marriage** is the act, ceremony, or process of formation of the legal relationship of two persons.
- **Civil union** is a registered partnership of two people being together as a couple, with rights and powers, similar to the ones acquired by marriage, granted by the law of their country of residence.
- **Adoption** is a legal action aimed at ensuring the welfare and protection of children, providing them with a permanent family willing to foster and legally represent them.
- **Step-child adoption** is the kind of adoption where a partner in a civil union, or other registered same-sex relationship, can adopt a biological and, in some cases, adopted child of the other partner.

Stakeholders and measures in place

The European Parliament (EP) and other EU bodies are already involved in the issue, but their powers are limited, due to the EU's **supporting competence** on the matter. The EP adopted [a resolution on the declaration of the EU as an LGBTIQ Freedom Zone](#), emphasising that “LGBTIQ

rights are human rights”. That was a rather symbolic act with regard to the current situation. The **European Commission** proposed [an initiative](#) aimed at ensuring that any kind of parenthood established in one Member State is recognised in another. It has recently gone through a feedback period and is awaiting public consultation. The 9th Article of [the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU](#) recognises the right to marry and to found a family as one of the fundamental rights of a person. However, it emphasises that this right is governed by respective national laws of Member States.

That makes **Member States** the primary stakeholders within the EU with the authority of recognising same-sex marriages and allowing adoption. Moreover, all of them, and the EU itself, are parties to [The Hague Convention on Protection of Children and Cooperation in Respect of Intercountry Adoption](#), which requires automatic cross-border recognition, yet only in cases when the adoptive parents and the adopted child come from two different countries. However, in cases when one of the countries is not a party to the above-mentioned convention, such intercountry adoption is regulated by bilateral agreements between them.

[ILGA-Europe](#) is an umbrella Non-Governmental Organisation (NGO) for local organisations, advocating equality for lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans and intersex people in Europe.

Key conflicts

The **differences in social acceptance of same-sex marriages is the primary source of conflict regarding LGBTIQ+ family rights**. People from different parts of Europe react to the issue in various ways, which leads to different approaches of their respective governments, driven by the will to represent societal needs and to meet their requests.

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the statement that same-sex marriages should be allowed throughout Europe? (%)

Source: [Eurobarometer on discrimination 2019](#)

This problem is then enhanced by the difficulties in [the cross-border recognition](#) of these families. There are Member States that recognise both foreign marriages and civil unions of people of the same sex regardless or, at least, recognise them as registered partnerships. However, there are also Member States that do not legally recognise same-sex marriages under any circumstances. This leads to situations when legally married same-sex couples are not recognised as such in some Member States, meaning that **they cannot enjoy rights and privileges given to them by their marital status**.

[Cross-border recognition of adoption](#) poses an even larger problem, as Member States have their own provisions regarding the recognition of adoption. There is no problem between states recognising same-sex adoption, but others may decide upon its recognition according to their respective national laws. So, there should be no significant issues with [Croatia allowing both registered and non-registered life partners to be the legal guardian of the child](#) regardless of orientation, and [Greece allowing same-sex couples to foster a child](#). However, on the 11th of March 2021, [Poland banned even single-parent adoption](#) – in order to prevent same-sex couples from adopting children. In December 2020, [the same was done by Hungarian authorities](#). Such decisions make it illegal to adopt a child by a same-sex couple. As such, **there is no legal guarantee that the adoption of a child by same-sex parents would be automatically recognised in another Member State**, bringing instability to these families, and impeding them from exercising other fundamental rights, such as freedom of movement.

Food for thought

Taking all the above into consideration, what measures should be taken to improve people's perception of recognition of same-sex marriage and adoption?

What stance should the EU take in this matter, considering that some Member States are actively moving against these rights?

What steps can be taken towards promoting same-sex couples' rights to legal recognition and the creation of a family?

How can the EU protect the rights of children adopted by same-sex couples and ensure recognition throughout all Member-States?

- [After 20 years of same-sex marriage in Europe, where is it legal now?](#) - Gary Parkinson for CGTN
- [Where Europe stands on gay marriage and civil unions](#) - Pew Research Center
- [Cross-border aspects of adoptions](#) - European Parliament

Introductory Clauses

- A. Keeping in mind that Article 9 of the [Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU](#) consolidates the right to marry and found a family, in accordance with national law,
- B. Noting with regret that only [13 out of 27](#) Member States fully recognise same-sex marriage and adoption,
- C. Noting with concern that social acceptance of same-sex marriage and adoption, in most of the countries that do not recognise them, is [lower than 40%](#),
- D. Emphasising that the rights of same-sex couples should be promoted and protected across the EU,
- E. Aware of the differences in current legislation regarding same-sex marriage and adoption among Member States,
- F. Concerned that variations in recognition of same-sex marriages and adoption hinder LGBTQI+ people's right to freedom of movement,
- G. Affirming the [European Parliament Resolution](#) on the Declaration of the EU as an LGBTQ Freedom Zone,
- H. Taking into account [the European Commission initiative](#) on cross-border recognition of parenthood;

Contacts

All general queries should be addressed to the Head Organiser of the Session. Any other, more specific queries may be taken up with the EYP Portugal. Matters of an academic nature will be dealt with by the Chairpersons, who will contact their Delegates directly.

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Head-Organiser

João Lopes

eventos@eyp.pt

+351 917 980 549

Session President

Leonor Rodrigues (PT)

leonor.rodrigues@eyp.pt

Associação Portuguesa do Parlamento Europeu dos Jovens

European Youth Parliament Portugal

Rua de Mouzinho da Silveira 234,

4000 Porto, Portugal

eyp.pt | geral@pejportugal.com

President of EYP Portugal

Teresa Sandeman

teresa.sandeman@eyp.pt

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